

EFFECTS OF ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITIONS ON DEFECT FORMATION DURING AUTOCLAVE PROCESSING

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Keywords: Autoclave processing, Defects, Corners, Environmental factors, Humidity

ABSTRACT

Primary load-bearing composite structures such as aircraft wings, rotor blades and sailing masts require a high laminate quality. This can be achieved by autoclave prepreg processing where, in addition to the vacuum pressure, high external pressures during curing provides further enhance consolidation. As a result, simple shaped parts can be manufactured with high fibre volume fractions typically above 60%, with void contents less than 1% [1]. However, defects such as wrinkling and voids are still being found within complex structures. This research investigates defect formation within the layup, debulking and consolidation stages of processing, and is focused on female moulded corners with high laminate thickness to corner radius ratios.

Experimental studies were carried out to investigate the effect of humidity exposure to uncured prepreg on defect formation during the steps of autoclave processing steps. It is hypothesized that moisture uptake influences prepreg characteristics such as compaction behaviour and prepreg tack, and therefore achieved quality following consolidation. In addition, the pressure distribution during debulking in corners, for laminates exposed to various humidity levels, was measured using the Tekscan pressure mapping system.

It was observed that defects already occur during the layup and debulking process, which then affect defect evolution in the subsequent autoclave curing process. It is also shown that humidity affects the prepreg characteristics and thereby the consolidation quality, resulting in a lower compaction pressure in corners, as measured by the Tekscan pressure mapping sensor.

1 INTRODUCTION

A traditional manufacturing method to produce high-performance structural fiber reinforced laminates is autoclave consolidation of prepreg. The associated high consolidation force within the autoclave curing process typically suppresses defects such as bridging, wrinkles and voids. However, whereas flat laminates can be produced almost defect free, more complex parts such as U-, T-, and L-shaped parts with high laminate thickness to corner radius ratios are prone to contain defects in corners. Common corner defects such as wrinkling and voids are presented in Figure 1. They can significantly reduce the structural performance of the cured part with a decrease in tensile strength up to 36% for a void content of 4% and a decrease in the compressive stress up to 30% with a wrinkling severity of 10° [2].

Figure 1: Common defects a) Wrinkling b) Voids and Porosity

Consequently, an increased design safety factor will be used that results in parts heavier than needed and increases the manufacturing costs. Previous studies investigated the effect of processing parameters including material characteristics, bagging configurations and laminate stacking sequences on defect formation in corners [3, 4]. Li et al. [4] found that a quasi-isotropic laminate results in a more uniform thickness evolution than $[90^\circ]_n$ laminates. In the study conducted by Hubert and Poursartip [3], the compaction and flow behaviour of complex laminates for various bagging and moulding conditions was studied. In agreement with the results of Li et al [4], they have shown a uniform cured laminate thickness in flat sections. Corner thickening occurred in concave corners with resin and defect accumulation such as wrinkles and voids. It was also stipulated that the laminate thickness to corner radius ratio and material properties (bulk factor and interplay friction coefficient) affect the consolidation pressure distribution in corners, leading to a low-pressure region in female corners which influences defect formation [5]. Additionally, an analytical compaction model able to predict the thickness variation between the flanges and the corner in L-shape laminate was proposed, considering geometrical and material properties [3]. Environmental effects such as temperature and relative humidity during autoclave processing are important factors that need to be considered in terms of defect formations. As the prepreg materials are exposed to the atmosphere prior to the autoclave consolidation process, the material will absorb moisture from the surrounding air, driven by the diffusion process. The moisture content is thereby controlled by the diffusion coefficient of the material which in turn is affected by environmental conditions such as ambient temperature and relative humidity. Several studies on how absorbed moisture drives void formation already exist, however they are more focused on the autoclave consolidation process of simple part geometries or focused on Out-Of-Autoclave processing [6, 7, 8]. Furthermore, there remains a lack of knowledge on the source of voids and how they develop through autoclave processing stages [6]. In a study conducted by Netzel et al. [12], the defect formation in L-shaped corners from the material constituents to each manufacturing step was investigated by measuring the laminate thickness evolution in corners with a non-destructive laser measurement method. The measurements have shown that corner thickening already occurs during the layup and debulking processes, indicating that defects are forming in the early stages of processing.

The effect of temperature and relative humidity on uncured prepreg material characteristics and their effect on defect formation in L-shaped corners within autoclave processing was investigated in this study. In addition, the effect of humidity on pressure distributions generated during debulking in concave moulds was investigated using the Tekscan pressure mapping system. With a deeper understanding of the contribution of each manufacturing step on final defect content, including the lay-up, debulking and consolidation steps, guidelines can be provided to eliminate critical defects whereby the manufacturing costs can be reduced.

2 EXPERIMENTATION

The material considered for this study is a unidirectional toughened prepreg material consisting of T700 standard modulus carbon fibres from Toray combined with the RS454S epoxy resin system from Hankuk with a resin weight fraction of 35%. Sample size and stacking sequence vary with each experiment and will be further discussed in the following sections.

2.1 Preliminary study on prepreg moisture absorption

Preliminary studies were conducted to determine the maximum moisture content absorbed prior to the autoclave consolidation process based on the diffusion process. Prepreg layers have been conditioned at 40% and 90% relative humidity (RH) at 21°C and the weight gain over time was measured. The diffusion coefficient could then be calculated as well as the time needed to fully saturate the prepreg material. Table 1 presents the maximal percentage weight gain for a single prepreg layer and the calculated diffusion coefficients for samples conditioned at 40% and 90% RH.

These values show good agreement with prepreg material diffusion coefficients found in the literature [9]. Based on these results, all samples within the following humidity related experiments were conditioned for 25 hours in environmental chambers, prior to the layup step, to ensure all layers are fully saturated.

Relative Humidity	Time until fully saturated (1 Layer)	Maximum relative weight gain	Diffusion Coefficient
40%	25 hours	0.12 %	1.2879E-12 m ² /s
90%	25 hours	0.25 %	1.2001E-12 m ² /s

Table 1: Prepreg maximum relative weight gain exposed to 40% and 90% RH at 21°C

2.2 Influence of ambient temperature and relative humidity on defect formation

For a qualitative overview on the effect of the relative humidity during autoclave processing on evolving defects, prepreg layups were produced under climate controlled conditions. To simulate realistic process conditions samples were laid up within environmentally controlled rooms at 40% and 90% RH, at a constant temperature of 21°C. A standard debulking process was applied after every fourth ply for 15 minutes at a vacuum pressure of 2kPa. To demonstrate the effect of the geometry complexity on defect formation, flat and U-shaped parts were produced, each consisting of 28 prepreg layers with a stacking sequence of 0°, ±45° and 90° fibre orientations. Sample dimensions are shown in Table 2. For each geometry three samples were produced. Each sample was cut into six pieces and four microscopy specimens were cut out from the middle area of the sample as demonstrated with red circles in Table 2. The void content and severity of wrinkling in corners after debulking and after autoclave consolidation were evaluated utilising microscopy image analyses.

Experiment	Samples	Specimen per sample	Laminate thickness [mm]	Proportion of ply orientations [%]			
				0° [300gsm]	-45° [150gsm]	+45° [150gsm]	90° [150gsm]
Flat Samples	3	4	5.7	60	15	15	10
Corner Samples	3	4	5.7	60	15	15	10
Flat Samples				Corner Samples			

Table 2: Sample configuration for humidity experiments

2.3 Compaction Experiment

The compaction experiment had two objectives. First, the sample configurations provided the compaction limits during processing with regard to humidity. Second, plots of the thickness evolution versus time were used to extract simulation model parameters that will later be deployed in a UMAT material characterisation subroutine, to be used in a novel corner defect simulation model. The UMAT code was previously developed by Belnoue et al. [11] and includes a novel hyper-viscoelastic model for the consolidation of toughened prepreg systems.

Adapting the experimental procedure explained in Nixon et al. [10], simple cross-ply specimens, pre-conditioned at 40%, 60% and 90% relative humidity, were loaded under compression, between two parallel plates, using a load controlled ramp-dwell program at various temperatures (20 °C to 80 °C). The program starts with an initial load of 60N followed by a 240 seconds dwell time. The load was then increased in 60N steps with an additional 240 seconds dwell time after each load step until reaching 360N in total which corresponds to autoclave pressure. Two different sample configurations were tested

as demonstrated in Figure 2. Cross plied specimens were stacked with alternating fibre orientations of 0° and 90° whereas blocked plied samples were stacked with four blocks of plies consisting of the same fibre direction to explore the effects of stacking sequences during compaction. Each specimen consisted of 16 single 300gsm prepreg plies which resulted in a total specimen thickness of 4.8mm. The specimen edges were left unconstrained so the material can flow in transverse direction (squeezing) during compaction. During the specimen layup debulking was applied for 10 min after every fourth laid-up ply with a vacuum pressure of 2kPa. A plastic film was placed between the gaps created by the overhanging plies to prevent the plies from sticking together. The plastic film was later removed before the compaction test. After the test, the compacted laminate thickness was measured using a digital calliper.

Figure 2: Compaction specimen configuration, adapted from Nixon et al. [10]

2.4 Prepreg Adhesion Measurements

The effect of humidity and relative ply orientation on prepreg adhesion during the layup process was investigated by utilizing a standard 90° peel-off test (ASTM D6862 – 11). A standard peel force rig was used within an Instron 5567 machine using a 1kN load cell. The bottom prepreg layer was fixed to the ground metal plate, using doubled sided tape, with varying prepreg ply orientations of 0° , 45° and 90° , whereas 0° plies were used for the peeled off layer for each experiment as illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Adhesion test setup and fibre orientations

In order to decrease the influence of the prepreg bending stiffness on the prepreg adhesion measurements, a 150gsm prepreg was used in this experiment instead of the 300gsm material. Tests were conducted with samples conditioned at 40%, 60% and 90% relative humidity. To simulate the adhesion force during layup the prepreg layers were bonded together using a metal roller with an application force of 25N. The metal roller was rolled over the laminate three times with a speed of approximately 10mm per second.

2.5 Pressure Distribution Experiments

As explained by Hubert et al. [3, 13], a low-pressure region will occur in concave corners during consolidation, considering geometrical and material properties under a no-slip condition. It is stated, that the pressure difference occurs due to the different laminate reaction stress between the flat and corner area. Figure 4 demonstrates the equilibrium of forces of a free-body diagram, where S_p is the bag surface and S_T the tool surface. Equation 1 expresses the relation between the applied pressure P to the tool reaction pressure $P_{avgtool}$ for a concave geometry. The pressure distribution is therefore dependent on the laminate thickness to corner radius ratio, as well as the difference of the laminate thickness before and after compaction (the bulk factor).

Figure 4: Free-body diagram of the corner of a laminate over a concave tool [13]

To quantify the effect of humidity on the compaction pressure distributions in corner areas during the debulking process, measurements were made of the pressure exerted on mould sidewalls and corners. A high resolution, thin and flexible pressure mapping sensor (Tekscan 5051) was used to record the compaction pressure in a female mould having a corner radius of 14mm. As shown in Figure 5, the Tekscan sensor was placed in the corner area of a mould coated with a Teflon film, avoiding friction between the tool and sensor interface. A perforated plastic film covered the prepreg on the top and bottom surfaces to prevent the prepreg from sticking to the sensor, while allowing the prepreg to move freely on the sensor surface during compaction. A breather material on top of the prepreg and perforated film ensured homogenous air evacuation during debulking. The setup was vacuum bagged, and a bag pleat placed along the corner prevented bag bridging. In each experiment, a vacuum pressure of 2 kPa was applied inside the vacuum bag. The Tekscan system enables measurement at 100 Hz, and export of each frame of data for post analysis. Each frame includes a data set of 1936 single pressure values generated by the 44 rows by 44 column sensel grid of the Tekscan sensor.

Figure 5: a) Tekscan pressure measurement experimental setup: a. vacuum bag, b. breather cloth, c. perforated film, d. Prepreg, e. Tekscan sensor, f. Teflon film b) Tekscan sensor

The specimens used in this experiment consisted of 16 plies with different stacking sequences of specimens with purely 0° fibre orientation, and specimens with an alternating fibre orientation between 0° and 90°. This enabled investigation of the effect of the fibre orientation on the pressure distribution in sharp corners. The pre-conditioned samples at 40% 60% and 90% relative humidity were laid up and debulked after every fourth laid up ply for 10 min at a vacuum pressure of 2kPa.

3 Results

3.1 Influence of ambient temperature and relative humidity on defect formation

Figure 6 shows representative examples of the microscopy images of the flat and corner samples after debulking and autoclave consolidation for samples produced at 40% and 90% RH. The average results of 12 flat and corner microscopy samples and the associated porosity values measured are presented in Figure 6b. The results show an increase in porosity in the corner samples produced at 90% RH for after both processing steps, debulking and consolidation. It can be concluded that humidity, already within the debulking process, leads to defects in complex geometries. These air voids can act as a nucleation side for vapour voids within the autoclave cure cycle, when the resin pressure is not sufficient enough to suppress the dissolved moisture to evaporate and diffuse into the air pockets.

Figure 6: a) Microscopy image analysis b) Void content for flat and corner samples

It can also be observed that with increasing geometric complexity and humidity, that the standard deviation for the cured samples is increasing. One explanation is that voids are unpredictable in their location and cross sections might or might not always be taken from an area including voids. However, the average result taken from 12 corner sections represents a clear effect of humidity on defect formation. Another explanation might be that prepreg layers conditioned at higher humidity levels lead to a higher variable layup quality due to changing material characteristics such as prepreg tack. Higher tack will make it more difficult for the laminator to form and adjust layers in corners and therefore increase the chance of ply bridging.

3.2 Compaction Experiment

The results for the compaction test of cross-plyed samples, conditioned at various humidity levels compacted at three different temperatures, are shown in Figure 7. Each line shows an average value from four samples. All samples were compacted at isothermal conditions of 20°C, 50°C and 80°C. The results clearly show that with a higher temperature, and the associated decrease of viscosity, higher levels of compaction could be achieved. The large gap between the 20°C and 50°C tests can be explained by the initial drop in resin viscosity between these temperatures.

Similar results are obtained for the blocked ply samples, shown in Figure 8. Overall, blocked ply samples show a higher degree of compaction, which can be explained by the higher squeezing deformation of the unidirectional stack of plies within the sample. Stacks of plies with the same fibre orientation exhibit less resistance to shear flow and the material viscosity is predominantly dependant on the resin viscosity. Conversely, in a cross-plyed arrangement, the compaction load is better supported by the fibre bed which results in a higher material viscosity behaviour.

Figure 7: Results of compaction test for Cross Plyed (CP) samples

Samples compacted at 50°C show a clear pattern in which the single load and dwell segments can easily be distinguished. In contrast, the ramp-dwell steps for samples compacted at 80°C only show an initial step and then merge into a more or less continuous compaction curve. It is expected that this phenomenon can be explained by the fact that the compaction limit per load cycle could not be reached within the 240 seconds dwell time, due to the low material viscosity at high temperatures that leads to high compactability. Therefore, each subsequent compaction cycle will directly merge into the next compaction cycle.

Additionally, a clear effect of the humidity can also be observed, where samples conditioned at higher humidity show a higher compaction rate. The influence of humidity is visible for all temperatures and the effect is increasing with increasing temperatures. The presumable cause might be a decrease in the

resin viscosity itself due to the absorbed moisture which will be investigated in future resin viscosity experiments.

Figure 8: Results of compaction tests for Blocked Plied (BP) samples

3.3 Prepreg Adhesion Measurements

The results presented in Figure 9 show a dependency of the adhesion force on the relative fibre direction, as well as a steady increase of adhesion force for higher humidity levels. The higher adhesion force affects the ability of the plies to slip relative to each other and to form properly into a corner during consolidation.

Figure 9: Average peel force depending on fibre orientation and humidity

3.4 Pressure Distribution Experiments

The compaction pressure exerted by a 4.8mm thickness prepreg laminate on the tool surface in a concave corner with a 14mm radius has been measured. The results in Figure 10 and Figure 11 show the effect of the fibre orientation and humidity on the pressure distribution, between the corner area and the

sidewall of the mould. Each line represents the average value of three samples and the associated standard deviations. It can be seen that both the fibre orientation and humidity affect the pressure distribution. Laminates with 0° and 90° plies decrease the compaction pressure in the corner to lower values, when compared to laminates consisting of only 0° plies.

This can be explained by the differences in the ply stiffness between the 0° and 90° plies. During compaction the laminate thickness changes. As a consequence, the plies closer to the bag side need to compensate for the radius change by slipping relative to each other. Due to the higher stiffness of the 0° plies, the laminate is restricted to form inside the mould radius especially if the plies are not able to slip relative to each other. As shown in the prepreg adhesion experiments, higher humidity leads to an increase in adhesion force which will affect the ability of a ply to slip, therefore decreasing the compaction pressure even further. In contrast, 90° plies can form more easily in the corner area during compaction, due to the lower ply stiffness [3, 4].

Figure 10: Pressure distributions 0° - Ply orientations

Figure 11: Pressure distributions 0°+90° - Ply orientations

It was also observed that during the layup process the 90% RH 0° plies were more likely to induce bridging during the hand layup process, which leads to a significant low-pressure region in corners that

could not be corrected by the subsequent debulking process. Figure 12a) shows an example of the full pressure distribution of a 90° laminate, whereas Figure 12b) shows the significant pressure reduction due to a bridged 0° degree ply after a 15 min debulking time. All samples that exhibited bridging were not included in the evaluation of the effect of humidity on corner pressure distribution.

Figure 12: Tekscan measurement pressure distribution; a) Pressure reduction without bridging in a 90° ply laminate, and b) significant pressure reduction due to bridging of a 0° ply

4 CONCLUSIONS

This experimental program has demonstrated that higher absorbed moisture content increases the risk of inducing ply bridging during the layup process, because of the higher tackiness of the prepreg plies. This may also result in a compaction pressure reduction during consolidation, as verified by the Tekscan pressure measurement experiments. Based on the analytical corner pressure prediction model presented by Brilliant and Hubert [13], the relative ability of plies to slip, and the bulk factor of the laminate during consolidation both play a significant role on the pressure distribution between the corner and sidewalls of the mould. Compaction experiments of cross-plyed prepreg laminates showed an increased bulk factor for samples conditioned at higher humidity, which in turn increases the distance the plies need to slip relative to each other in order to fully conform to the given corner geometry. Additionally, an increased adhesion force at higher humidity could be measured, which decreases the ability of plies to slip. Both parameters thereby affect corner pressure reduction. Thus, the debulking process is not sufficient to suppress these air voids, and they will act as a nucleation site for vapour voids during the autoclave consolidation step. Moreover, an increased number of 0° ply orientation within the laminates reduced the compaction pressure further.

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